

An Analytical Study of Student Learning Outcomes and their Alignment with the Activities of Writing Skill at Primary Level in Pakistan

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to analyze the 'Single National Curriculum 2020' and its implementation at the primary level in Pakistan, with a specific focus on the student learning outcomes (SLOs) in English as outlined in the SNC. This analysis will be conducted in relation to the alignment of these outcomes with the activities presented in the Grade-V English textbook published by the Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board in Lahore. To achieve this objective, a qualitative approach has been employed. The study involved a comprehensive document analysis of the SLOs and the activities pertaining to the development of writing skills in the Grade-5 English curriculum. The primary focus was on assessing the alignment of the SLOs as outlined in the SNC English Book-V with the writing exercises presented in the textbook. The results of this analysis reveal that a majority of the SLOs are in harmony with the activities designed to enhance writing skills. However, there are some minor alignment issues, as well as occasional grammatical and typing problems that were identified. This study serves to enhance our understanding of the practical implementation of the 'SNC 2020,' specifically in terms of how well it aligns with the prescribed textbook. Furthermore, the findings of this research can be beneficial for teachers, providing them with clarity regarding the fulfillment of the intended objectives for improving students' writing skills at the primary level in Pakistan.

Keywords: English textbook, SNC, SLOs, writing skill, creative writing

1. Introduction

A document that contains an overall educational program including whatever experience a learner has in school is called curriculum. To provide a roadmap that has obvious goals and certain objectives is the purpose of the curriculum. These things are planned according to a framework or research which presents a professional practice (Kelly, 2009). According to Doll (2013), a document that is distributed by a federal government or state is called curriculum. He further explains that a school curriculum is the collection of topics, aspects and processes that are formal and informal with the help of which the students get knowledge and comprehension. Under the patronage of a certain school, curriculum works as a roadmap for those learners who get skills, attain certain attitudes and certain values.

'Single National Curriculum' is a curriculum having a single vision with the concept of education for all based on a planned series of syllabus containing students' learning outcomes similar for all types of educational institutions in Pakistan. It was the wish of the majority of Pakistani masses to have a single national curriculum due to the reason of inherent disparity among different sections of society. Under the guidance of the Prime Minister of Pakistan, the vision of one nation, one curriculum was materialized in 2020 by launching the first phase of single national curriculum at the primary level and is going to be implemented this year i.e. 2021 at the primary level for all sections to provide justice and equality in education and as a result to have equal opportunities in economic and social status. The purpose of single national curriculum is to provide competent, vigilant, responsible citizens and a hardworking generation for the future.

Students' learning outcomes are a plan of action for an academic course that students will achieve successfully at the end of the academic year. This success can only be materialized if this plan is communicated successfully on paper. Gosling and Moon (2001) are of the view that the teaching approach that is based on learning outcomes is becoming popular at the international level.

Learning outcomes are just like a navigation tool. Once you have set the location of your destination, it will guide you throughout the journey and will lead you to the destination correctly without losing the way. Even if you take a wrong direction, it guides you to reach the intended destination through the next nearest route. Similar is the case with learning outcomes; it is a type of guiding tool that enables the students to attain desired results. It also creates harmony between teacher and student to attain similar aims having different positions. So, SLOs are the statements in written form that give a plan of action to be achieved by the students at the end of the academic year (Adam, 2004). Students' learning outcomes are the statements of what a student is expected to have knowledge, understanding and be able to perform at the end of the learning process (ECTS Users' Guide, 2005).

In light of this context, the present study investigates the integration of writing skills within the curriculum, as well as the alignment of SLOs presented at the outset of each lesson with the writing activities featured in the textbook exercises.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To assess the efficacy of content and exercises in English textbooks at the primary level in alignment with SLOs.

1.2 Research Questions

The research seeks to address the following questions:

- To what extent is the content and exercises in the primary-level English textbook aligned with the SLOs outlined in the 'SNC'?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Curriculum

According to Nunan (1993), there are many contradictory opinions regarding the distinction between syllabus design and development, so he finds it pertinent to start the discussion with commenting on and clarifying the available definitions of the terms 'syllabus' and 'curriculum'. He propounds, in this regard, the possibility of marking the line of cleavage between the narrow and broad approaches to designing the syllabus. Candlin (1984) is of the view that curriculum appertains to general statements regarding language learning, its purpose, process, assessment, and the role of the students and teachers in this process as well as their relationship. On the contrary, syllabi are more localized and have their basis on the details and data concerning the actual happenings in the class when teachers and students are engaged in applying some curriculum to their situations.

2.2 SNC

One nation and one curriculum is public representing initiative taken by newly elected govt. to universalize educational system in Pakistan. This uniformity and integrity was a prior need of time to provide equal educational opportunities to both public and private sector which is magnificently done by current govt. of Pakistan. So, newly launched single national curriculum can be considered as a great milestone towards the great slogan of one nation and one curriculum which is developed with partnership of public and private stakeholders to fulfill the basic needs of student and having equal educational opportunities for all nation through this newly developed curriculum.

National Educational Policy Framework, 2018 (MoFEPT, 2018), suggested the adoption of multi-lingual policy in Pakistan in which the role of English would be that of L2. Accordingly, the curriculum frameworks were revised and reviewed, throughout the country, including the revision of the common national standards of teaching and learning along with the identification of common standards which could be applied in all kinds of school system in all the provinces. With this vision, the National Curriculum for English Language 2006 was gradually revised for making it in line with the ever evolving local as well as international demands. In 2017, the first review took place for updating the curriculum for Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT) schools. The next phase of review came in 2019 with a view to elaborating the Single National Curriculum (SNC), in accordance with the vision of the government, for all streams of education.

2.3 SLOs

According to Adam (2004), what the successful learner is to be capable to attain at the completion of course, unit of module are called SLOs which are the statements in written form. SLOs are written statements of what a learner is estimated to learn, comprehend or to have capability to show at the end of the process of learning. SLOs calculate whether learner achieve competences in their process of learning (Weinert, 2001).

Stern and Roseman (2004) ask if difference in student learning is necessitated by improved curriculum materials. Instinctively, it appears that the answer to this question would be in the affirmative. Particularly, according to Chambliss and Calfee (1989), both theoretically and practically, better-designed textbook of sciences should increase the understanding of the students.

To produce outputs rather than inputs is the main root of outcome based education. Rather than lecture-based approach as in the conservative loom, the learning process mainly deals with the student-centered approach. Outcome based education means, as defined in Spady (1994: 1), focusing on the development of the students and planning everything in a system of education around what is necessary for all learners to have capability to perform exceptionally at the end of their experiences related to learning. The basis of outcome based education is the learning of students; the idea of successful learning of students is more significant than time and manner in which they learn. (Spady, 1994: 8).

Discussing about the advantages of learning outcomes Ruhland and Brewer (2001) argued that SLOs should not only show what knowledge the learners have, but they should also grasp the improvements happened in their development related to cognitive and affective side during the learning experiences. Goh (2017) conducted a study to find out effects of course design, interaction with peers, instructors and students on SLOs and satisfaction in E-learning. The study confirmed the experiences of the learners have positive effects on outcomes of learning and e-learning satisfaction. The study concludes that student's interaction is very important to get good results in e-learning. Blaug (1970) suggested that there is a strong relationship between educational outcomes, particularly SLOs, and personal earnings. He argued that education can be extended if it improves individuals' income (Blaug, 1983). Schultz (1963) categorized educational outcomes into two types: investment and consumption.

2.4 Importance of Writing

Writing comprises a process of thinking which need complete and conscious efforts and time on the part of a writer says McCrimon (1988) in his book "Writing with a Purpose". Text in written form is produced by the raw material that may be crafted by the creative mind of the writer. According to Hyland (2004), the skill of writing is essential for the proficiency of language which includes the capability to articulate effectively one's ideas and thoughts during cross-cultural communication.

The art of writing is a multifaceted process that encompasses not only the transcription of language input but also the development of genre and the internalization of knowledge. These skills rely on a combination of abilities and talents (Badger & White, 2000). Godwin and Perkins (1998 & 2002) argue that young children bring a wealth of experience, knowledge, and imaginative thinking with them when they begin school. It is crucial to provide an environment that nurtures these experiences. De Bono (cited in Curtis, 1998) concurs, stating that children can be exceptional thinkers.

Brindley and Schneider (2002) assert that writing skills are the most critical for student success among the four language skills. Writing is a complex skill that requires effort, and comparing writing with other language skills is a multifaceted task (Shawis, 2009).

Flower and Hayes (1981) suggested in the context of English writing that there are three common stages of the process of writing, i.e. pre-writing, while writing and post writing. Students usually use planning to set goal, organise and generate their ideas for writing (Chien, 2012). In the process of writing students translate their ideas into discernible words, sentences and paragraphs and inspect what has been planned or written for improvement (Chien, 2012; de Larios, Manchón, Murphy, & Marín, 2008). They word on feedback in post writing from peers, teachers or parents and review the problems related to grammar and lexis that appear in their writing. According to Harmer (2001), imaginative tasks such as poetry, story and play writing is creative writing.

3. Research Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research method. Document analysis will serve as the primary approach to investigate the alignment between the SLOs outlined in the SNC of 2020 and the content of the Grade 5 English textbook. Document analysis is a well-established method in research, as recognized by Hancock and Algozzine (2006). Creswell (2012) also highlights the significance of documents in providing qualitative researchers with essential insights into the subject of study.

The research process involves two key steps. Firstly, the study acquired the documents containing the 'SLOs (SLOs) outlined in the SNC for English 2020 (Grade V).' A comprehensive analysis was conducted to gain a thorough understanding of the SLOs specified in the SNC, particularly focusing on the expected proficiencies in English writing skills. Subsequently, document analysis of the Grade 5 English textbook published by the Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board was carried out. This analysis involved an examination of the SLOs presented at the beginning of each unit within the English textbook for Grade 5. The alignment of these learning outcomes with the activities found in the writing exercises section of the textbook was thoroughly assessed.

4. Results and Description

4.1 Description of Writing Section Book-V

English book of 'SNC' for Grade-5 by Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board, Lahore contains 14 units. Every unit of the book consists of seven parts. The first part of the book is 'Unit No. and Name' with 'SLOs'. Second part is with the heading of 'Getting Started' that aims at brainstorming about the topic students are going to study with some questions related to brainstorming in 'Let's Talk'. The third part of the unit starts with pre-reading activity, then actual lesson starts and at the end of this part is the post reading activity. The fourth part of the lesson starts with the exercise 'Oral Communication' with the sub-headings of 'Learning the Sounds' and 'Learning to Speak'. Next part is the 'Reading and Critical Thinking' which focuses on 'Reading Comprehension' and 'Analytical Reading'. The sixth part is 'Language Focus' containing 'Vocabulary Building', 'Learning to Spell' and 'Grammar' sub-sections. The last part of the unit contains exercises of 'Writing' under the sub-headings of 'Learning to Write' and 'Creative Writing'.

The learning outcome of writing skill for the Unit-1 with the unit title of 'Patience' starts with the writing of multi-syllable words with correct spelling which is aligned with the activities in 'Learning to Write' to read the given multi-syllable words first and then in the next activity to divide the given words into their syllables and also to write the number of syllables notebook. Next SLO is to analyse a simple paragraph to recognize that a paragraph comprises a group of sentences that develops a single main idea, and a main idea of a paragraph is given in the topic sentence and other sentences in the paragraph support the topic sentences is aligned with the activity to read the first paragraph of the lesson carefully, write its topic sentence and supporting details and also to write its main idea in own words using correct capitalisation. Then the learning outcome is to analyse and use the above organising principles of paragraph writing to write a meaningful and unified paragraph is aligned in the activity in 'Creative Writing' to write some good qualities which you can show in school/classroom. Also write how they would help you in becoming a better person with the use of correct punctuation and capitalisation. Unit-2 starts with the first learning outcome to write a paragraph to describe/show sequence in a picture/series of pictures and second learning outcome is to analyse and use conjunctions e.g. and, but, or, because, transitional words, e.g. for example, for instance, therefore and sequence markers, e.g. first(ly), second(ly), then, next, etc which is aligned with reading the given paragraph and notice the use of conjunctions and then to write sentences using above conjunctions in notebook. Then for the purpose to let the students know about the transitional words first of all students are asked to read the given sentences and notice the use of transitional words and then to make two sentences using the above transitional words. Another activity though not included in learning is to circle the things from given items that you need for making a card then to write the procedure to make a card. In 'Creative Writing' students are asked to write by their own any incident of their life when they treated somebody with kindness. Unit-3 contains two SLOs. First learning outcome requires the learners to recognise and use more action verbs from an extended environment including other academic subjects in speech and writing which is aligned with the activity in the book under the heading of 'Learning to Write' of this unit to read the speech bubbles and then to fill in speech bubbles given in the exercise. The second learning outcome is to write short text in speech bubbles and cartoon strips using vocabulary, tone, style of expression appropriate to the communicative purpose and context aligned with writing a biography of the favourite personality in the notebook of the students. Review-1 evaluates the learning through paragraph writing on the topic "Health is Wealth" with addition to label the topic sentence and supporting details.

Next portion of the book contains next three chapters and then review of these chapters. Unit-4 has only one learning outcome that is to use appropriate vocabulary and tenses to write a simple paragraph by giving a physical description and character traits/characteristics of person/object/place, moving from general to specific is aligned with the third activity that is to write a short paragraph about the "Benefits of Trees". However, there are also two more activities to read the dialogues given in speech bubbles and then to fill in these speech bubbles while in 'Creative Writing' students are asked to share their experiences if they have any adventure or experience in their lives. The first learning outcome of Unit-5 is to write a guided paragraph using ideas gathered and organised through various strategies which is aligned in the activity under the heading of 'Learning to Write' to read the given mind map and write a paragraph about climate change in their notebooks while the second learning outcome to select and use some strategies, e.g. brainstorming, mind mapping or making outlines, etc. to gather and organise ideas for their own writing is aligned with the activity to make a mind map about your favourite season and write a few sentences about it. Moreover, these learning outcomes are strengthened in 'Creative Writing' to write a paragraph about the 'Importance of Natural Environment' in notebook with the help of word bank. First learning outcome of Unit-6 is to identify narrative paragraph to note differences and second SLO is to use appropriate vocabulary and tenses to write a simple paragraph by narrating an activity from the immediate surroundings is aligned with the activity to read the given narrative paragraph and then to write a narrative paragraph about any memorable incident of their school life. To improve self-writing in 'Creative Writing', the activity to write a paragraph on how you spend your time at home during the coronavirus lockdown and also mention any new skill you learnt during this lockdown. To evaluate the writing skill learnt in this section of three chapters, Review-2 requires writing a narrative paragraph about the most memorable journey of their life.

The first learning outcome Unit-7 is to identify the elements of a story: plot, beginning, middle and the end of a story with conflict and resolution; human, animal, imaginary characters and their roles; setting and second SLO to write a guided story using the elements of story writing which are aligned with activity in exercise which require writing a story about favourite animals and also to note the elements of the fable learnt previously from the 'reading section' in notebook. Moreover, these learning outcomes strengthened through the activity given in 'Creative Writing' to write a story with the moral 'A Friend in Need is a Friend Indeed'. Unit-8 contains three learning outcomes among which first SLO to read short notes written for different purposes to write short notes of their own to friends and family members and second SLO to write short informal invitation for a variety of purposes to demonstrate the use of conventions of short invitations are aligned with the first activity of 'Learning to Write' which require writing a short invitation to your friend to attend your birthday party. While the third SLO to write replies accepting or declining an invitation is aligned with the activity to write a short note accepting the invitation above. 'Creative Writing' requires writing about an incident in your life in which you felt disappointed. Describe it in your own words. How did you deal with it? The first SLO of Unit-9 is to write central idea of a given poem in simple language which is aligned with the first activity of the exercise to read the central idea given in the activity and with the second activity to read the poem and write the central idea of the poem. The second learning outcome is not aligned with any activity as it asks to enlist rhyming words and write a poem based on the central idea. 'Creative Writing' activity is to 'write what you want to be when you grow up so you can serve your country. Why do you want to do it?' Unit-10 Eid-ul-Azha doesn't have any SLO to be aligned with the exercise. However, there are some activities of writing in 'Learning to Write' first of which is 'Suleman and his sister made a dessert for an Eid party. Let's read what recipe they followed for making 'Chocolate Banana Pops'.' While second activity is to find the recipe of favourite dish on the internet and write it in notebook. Activity in 'Creative Writing' is to write a paragraph on the topic "A Good Day with My Family". This portion of four units is evaluated through a writing activity of a story writing on the topic 'A Lion and the Mouse' with a moral in Review-3.

Unit-11 starts with the learning outcome to use reading texts as models for the own writing of the students is aligned with the activity in 'Learning to Write' to look at the mind map and write about some 'Qualities of a Good Person'. You can add more qualities to the mindmap and further through the activity with the use of information given above to write a dialogue about 'Qualities of a Good Person' in own words in the notebook is also aligned with the first SLO. Second SLO that asks to write a short passage, anecdote, fable, etc. for pleasure and creativity doesn't have any activity in the exercise. Third activity requires revision of the written work as it asks to 'Revise written work for correct spelling and punctuation, pronoun-antecedent agreement, subject-verb agreement' doesn't align directly with any activity. In 'Creative Writing' students are required to write some ways to save their money and how they can use it. There are two learning outcomes of Unit-12 the of which is about the recognition of function of different question words to write appropriate short answer is aligned with the activity to write a paragraph on 'National Bird of Pakistan' in students' notebooks keeping in mind the questions given at the end of the activity. Second learning outcome of this unit 'Complete a simple paragraph using the given words, phrases and sentences' doesn't align with any activity in the exercises of writing. Paragraph writing on 'Endangered Animals' and to write about the steps you can take to save these animal in 'Creative Writing'. Unit-13 starts with the learning outcome of the use of conventions of letter writing: address, date, salutation, body and closing etc. is aligned to the activity to some extent to read the given letter and notice its features. Next three SLOs a. write an informal letter and formal letter or Application; b. Write a reply to a short informal letter from friends and family members; c. Revise written work for layout, legibility and vocabulary are aligned to some extent to the activity in 'Creative Writing' to write a letter to the editor of any children's magazine about pollution in your area. Unit-14 contains two learning outcomes. First SLO is to write central idea of a given poem in simple language is aligned with the activity in exercise to read the given poem and write its central idea in notebook while the second learning outcome to enlist rhyming words and write a poem based on the same central idea is aligned with the activity to write three pairs of rhyming words about 'Rainbows' and write a poem in notebook. To enhance self-writing, the activity to share the views in writing a paragraph on 'How Should we Take Care of Our Pet Animals'. To evaluate the last portion of Book-5, the activity of writing a letter to friend telling him/her about recent visit to Neelam Vally is given in Review-4.

5. Discussion

The first aim of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of SLOs-based content and exercises in English textbooks at the primary level. The writing skill portion of Unit-1, Grade-V begins with the syllabic division of words, which not only helps students understand English languagemorphology but also improves their spelling comprehension. Rehman (2002) highlighted that many Pakistani students struggle due to their tendency to cram information. They often fail to write in accordance with the rules and techniques described by English essay writing expertssuch as Hyland (1990). Mullens (1993) suggests that effective teaching can be measured by students' learning outcomes, emphasizing the importance of setting clear goals through SLOs.

The learning outcomes for paragraph writing in this book commence with the first unit. The techniques of essay writing start with composing paragraphs, and students are advised to read the first paragraph of the lesson and write its topic sentence, supporting details, and main idea in their own words. This approach aims to improve their writing in a coherent manner. The alignment of learning outcomes to enhance paragraph writing skills is further reinforced through creative writing. In this context, students are encouraged to write about the positive qualities they can exhibit in the classroom and explain how these qualities can help them become better individuals. Eisner and Vallance (1974) emphasize the self-actualization approach, primarily concerned with promoting personal growth and development.

Effective writing should not only express ideas creatively using various writing techniques but also adhere to proper grammar. To address this, the SLO "to analyze and use conjunctions (e.g., and, but, or, because), transitional words (e.g., for example, for instance, therefore), and sequence markers (e.g., first(ly), second(ly), then, next, etc.)" is introduced. This SLO is first introduced through the definition and examples of conjunctions in a paragraph within the exercise. Then, students are tasked with writing a paragraph using the conjunctions they've learned. A similar approach is used for transitional words and sequence markers. The aim is to guide students in writing coherently and logically.

Unit-2 continues to build on these learning outcomes, with a focus on writing paragraphs to describe a sequence of events and using conjunctions, transitional words, and sequence markers effectively. Additionally, students are encouraged to read sentences containing transitional words and then create their sentences using these words. Another activity involves selecting items needed to make a card and writing the procedure for making it. In the "Creative Writing" section, students are asked to write about an incident in their lives when they treated someone with kindness.

Unit-3 emphasizes writing using speech bubbles to express a character's thoughts or words. The use of action verbs is a key learning outcome, which is reinforced by the exercise's content. By using pictures that depict various actions, students are encouraged to incorporate action verbs into their speech bubbles. This approach aligns with the notion that students' learning outcomes demonstrate their increased knowledge and understanding as a result of their educational experiences (Entwistle, 1997).

Unit-4 focuses on descriptive paragraph writing, with an emphasis on correct spelling and punctuation, pronoun-antecedent agreement, and subject-verb agreement. Although there is only one learning outcome related to writing descriptive paragraphs, additional activities, such as reading dialogues in speech bubbles and writing dialogues, are provided. The expository paragraph writing activity on the topic "Benefits of Trees" aligns with the learning outcome and introduces students to expository writing, where the aim is to inform, define, explain, clarify, and instruct.

The learning outcomes of Unit-5 center on writing guided paragraphs using ideas gathered and organized through various strategies, as well as selecting and using strategies like brainstorming, mind mapping, or making outlines to gather and organize ideas for their own writing. These learning outcomes are aligned with activities that guide students in writing paragraphs while utilizing different strategies. Students also practice these skills through creative writing, where they write a paragraph about the "Importance of Natural Environment" using a word bank.

Unit-6 continues the focus on narrative writing. Students are introduced to narrative paragraphs and encouraged to read a paragraph that retells an event or story with a beginning, middle, and end. This guides them to write a narrative paragraph about any memorable incident from their school life. The "Creative Writing" activity prompts students to write a paragraph about how they spent their time at home during the coronavirus lockdown and any new skills they acquired during that period. To assess the writing skills learned in this section, Review-2 requires students to write a narrative paragraph about the most memorable journey of their life.

Unit-7 concentrates on storytelling, introducing elements such as plot, conflict, resolution, characters (human, animal, and imaginary), and setting. Students engage in writing activities that align with these learning outcomes, including writing a story about their favorite animals and analyzing the elements of fables they've learned. Creative writing encourages students to write a story with the moral "A Friend in Need is a Friend Indeed."

Unit-8 emphasizes the importance of writing short notes and short informal invitations for various purposes, demonstrating the conventions of short invitations. Activities in the exercise align with these learning outcomes, requiring students to write short invitations for a birthday party and write short notes accepting the invitations. The "Creative Writing" section invites students to write about an incident in their lives when they felt disappointed, encouraging self-reflection and expression.

Unit-9 returns to the realm of poetry, with learning outcomes focused on understanding the central idea of a given poem in simple language and listing rhyming words, followed by writing a poem based on the central idea. Activities in the exercise align with these objectives, and the "Creative Writing" activity encourages students to write about what they aspire to be when they grow up and how they can serve their country.

Unit-10, dedicated to Eid-ul-Azha, focuses on informal writing, as there are no direct learning outcomes related to writing skills. Students are guided to read a dessert recipe and search for their favorite dish recipe on the internet, then write it in their notebooks. The "Creative Writing"

activity prompts students to write a paragraph about "A Good Day with My Family." Review-3 evaluates writing skills through a story writing activity on the topic "A Lion and the Mouse" with a moral.

Unit-11 aims to use reading texts as models for students' writing. The learning outcomes are aligned with activities that require students to write about the qualities of a good person and engage in dialogues about these qualities. Additionally, students are encouraged to write short passages, anecdotes, or fables for pleasure and creativity, although no specific activities related to these learning outcomes are provided in the exercise. Revision and proofreading activities are suggested to refine written work.

Unit-12 introduces different question words and their functions, aligning with the learning outcomes that focus on writing appropriate short answers and completing paragraphs using given words, phrases, and sentences. Creative writing encourages students to write about what they want to be when they grow up and why. Review-4 evaluates this section through a letter writing activity, asking students to write a letter to a friend about their recent visit to Neelam Valley.

Unit-13 emphasizes the conventions of letter writing, including address, date, salutation, body, and closing. The learning outcomes are aligned with activities that introduce students to these conventions. Additional learning outcomes involve writing informal and formal letters or applications and writing replies to short informal letters from friends and family members. Although these objectives are aligned with letterwriting activities

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis indicates that the majority of the learning outcomes in the Grade-5 English textbook align well with the activities presented in the exercises. This alignment is beneficial for both teachers and students, as it provides clear objectives for what students are expected to learn by the end of each unit. The textbook covers various dimensions of writing skills, including descriptive and narrative paragraph writing, dialogues, poems, and letter writing, which helps in developing a comprehensive skill set. However, there are some units (such as Unit 4, 9, 11, 12, 13) where the learning outcomes do not align perfectly with the activities in the exercises. Additionally, there are typographical errors in Units 4 and 13, which should be corrected for clarity and accuracy. Overall, the Grade-5 English textbook appears to be a valuable resource for teachers, providing a clear framework for English language instruction. It offers a diverse range of writing activities to enhance students' writing skills. With some adjustments to improve alignment and correct typographical errors, it can continue to be a useful guide for educators and students alike.

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Bio-note:

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